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Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)

Md. Anowar Hossain

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for production engineers, textile engineers, color engineers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of textile dyeing & finishing. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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WPT-402, Wet processing Tech-IV

Course instructor: Engr. Samrat Jatin

Blend dyeing: Blends are any textile material from fibre through yarn to fabric, which are deliberate combination of chemically or physically different fibrous polymers.

Example: cotton and polyester blend is an example of chemically different blend and that of cotton and viscose (both are cellulosic) is physically different blend.

*** Write down the reason of blending?

১. Economy: ^{↑ ভরসীকরণ} Dilution of an expensive, lustrous fibre by blending with a cheaper substitute.

Example: Viscose/cotton, Polyester/cotton
cotton/Acrylic

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Durability : To incorporate of more durable component to extend the useful life, e.g. Cotton spun yarn.

Physical property : A compromise to take advantage of desirable performance characteristics, contribute by both fibre component.

Example : Polyester/cotton blend to get comfort of cotton and strength and increase recovery of polyester.

Color : The development of novel fabric design for garments incorporating multicolor effect. Say- Polyester part is dyed and cotton part undyed.

Appearance : The presence of attractive appearance using by combination of yarn of different luster, crimp is possible by blending.

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Other properties:

1. Colourant modification is possible by blending.

2. Finishing process modification

3. Improve moisture absorption

4. Reduce lanolin-like characteristics, pilling etc.

Write down the percentage of different combination of blend dyeing is listed below:

1. Polyester/cotton blend is done - 58.4%
(major blend)
 2. Polyester/viscose blend is done - 20.4%
 3. Polyester/wool blend is done - 7.1%
 4. Wool/Acrylic blend is done - 1.4%
 5. Nylon/wool blend is done - 0.8%
 6. Synthetic/synthetic blend is done - 1.8%
 7. Cotton/synthetic (other than Polyester) - 1.1%
 8. Miscellaneous blend is done - 9.5%
- 100%

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Write down the factors affecting the choice of dyeing?

Ans:

1. Colouristic effect required i.e. solid, contrast.
2. Colour fastness, required of the resulting dyeing.
3. Suitability of dyeing for subsequent finishing process.
4. Compatibility of dyes from different application.
5. Availability of Particular type of bath batch, semi-continuous and continuous dyeing equipment.
6. Cost of dyes and chemical involved
7. Economic of the overall process.

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Second class

Date - 18.06.09

*** Write down the types of dye bath with
disperse/ reactive combination

Ans:

1. conservative / two bath process
2. Rapid / one bath process
3. less conservative / Reverse two bath process

4. Bayer dye method.

(Scientist)

*** Write down the contrast features of D/D
dye combination.

Ans:

1. Dispersions of disperse dye is stable only in acidic medium (pH → 4.5-5.5). But reactive dyeing is done in alkaline (pH → 8.0-10.5). In alkaline medium disperse dye degradation occurs.

ie Dispersions of disperse dye (ক্ষয়করক)

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2. For disperse dye x-stain in cotton, to remove this, reduction cleaning is done by hydrosol and caustic. For this treatment, some reactive dye (60%) is stripping out. For this reason, some selected disperse dye is use which don't create x-stain on cotton.

3. Huge amount of electrolyte (say-80 g/l) is needed for reactive dyeing, but for using electrolyte dispersion of disperse dye become unstable (inconstant/ অস্থির)

4. Dyeing of polyester fibre with disperse dye occurring at high temp. But at high temp. reactive start to be hydrolysed.

There are the problem of D/R combination and for this reason consecutive two bath process (separate bath) is used. (সম্মিলিত)

(x-stain = combination effect of colour on fabric)

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Discuss about consecutive / two bath process (separate bath) / Discontinuous dyeing / open end

Ans: In two bath process, by exhaust method at first polyester part of P/E blend is dyed with disperse dye, then cotton part is dyed with reactive dye. This is completely separate dyeing. Now the process is described below:

Recipe:

1. Disperse dye - 1% owf
2. Dispersing agent - (1-2) %
3. Acetic acid - (2-3) %
4. Temperature - 130°C
5. Time - 2 hrs.
6. M:L ratio - 1:10

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Procedure:

1. The bath is set with substrate at room temperature i.e. 50°C.
2. Non-ionic surfactant is added in dye bath.
3. Fabric is passed and dye bath is run for 15 minutes.
4. The temperature is raised from 50°C to (85-90)°C.
5. Dye solution and Auxiliaries are added.
6. pH is checked with CH_3COOH (4.5-5.5).
7. Temp. is raised at 130°C.
8. Dye bath is run for 45-60 minutes at 130°C.
9. The shade of fabric is checked.
10. Dye bath is dropped and carry on the 35 shade after treatment process.
match then

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Cotton patch dyeing with reactive dye:

Recipe :

- (1) Dye - 3%
- (2) Common salt 50 g/L
- (3) Soda ash - 15 g/L
- (4) Temperature - 60°C x 60'
- (5) M:L = 1:10

Curve of dyeing is given below:

Fig: Dyeing curve of cotton patch dyeing with reactive dye on p/c blend fabric.

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Asterc treatment of cotton part dyeing

↓
Cold wash ($<60^{\circ}\text{C}$)

↓
Hot wash (80°C)

↓
Soaping with detergent
($70-80^{\circ}\text{C}$)

↓
Hot wash

↓
Cold wash

↓
Neutralizing with CH_3COOH

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*** Write down the continuous dyeing of
polyester/cotton blend (woven)

Ans: The most suitable process for continuous
method of p/c blend dyeing is done in follow-
ing stages:-

Padding

Pre dye drying

Dyeing

The removal unit (cutting)

Chemical pad

steaming chamber

wash off

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Padding: Padding is a process by which chemical addition is occurred

Pre-drying: Heat is applied in low temp.

Drying: Heat is applied in high temp.

Thermofixation: Fixation is occurred.

Chemical pad: Addition of reactive dye, salt, soda.

Steaming chamber: Heat is applied to

Wash off: Washing is completed to

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Procedure:

1. The bath is set with substrate at room temp. i.e. 40°C/50°C
2. Antimigrants, Auxiliaries and dye stuff are added uniformly in padding zone.
3. Fabric is passed into padding zone and squeezed in done by squeezing roller.
4. Pre-drying is done for (1-2) min to decrease the moisture of fabric and dye stuff is added on the fabric surface.
5. Drying is occurred for (1-3) min at (60-70)°C and dye stuff is added inner surface of the fabric.
6. After that, fabric is passed into thermal unit and fixation of dye stuff is occurred.
7. After cooling, chemical padding is occurred to decrease the unevenness.
8. Fabric is passed into steamer (10-15) min.
9. Finally, fabric is passed into washing unit and drying chamber.
10. Finally delivery is occurred.

5. side col

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Primitive common
And discuss about in Damage in bleaching :

Bleaching is done in alkaline condition and high temperature (110°C). In alkaline condition and high temperature cellulose may easily oxidized into a variety of product known as oxi-cellulose.

Reaction :

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Here produce cacons in deposit on the fabric and does not remove in normal wash and it can't be identified by eye normally. It creates a sticky effect on fabric & surface. As a result uneven dyeing, printing occurred in place of precipitated cacons. It leads harsh feeling.

Remedy:

To remove harsh feeling scouring is done by less than 1% Hell's.

Scouring in acid treatment to remove harsh feeling.

Scouring is must when hypochlorite bleaching is done.

Mid-term
Chloramine reaction:

Even after scouring some residual protein remains in cotton. This protein reacts with HOCl and creates chloramine (NCl)

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1
n't
xltD

Forc reaction permanency of white appearance
in gas out.

When the fabric is subjected to dampening condition, -NCl reacts with H₂O and produce hypochlorous acid.

Thus HCl degrade the cotton fibre and cause yellowing effect of fabric and reduce permanency of whiteness.

Remedy: To protect the chloramine formation, Antichloro treatment in close close with strong reducing agent hydrazine and caustic antichloro treatment separates -Cl from -NH₂ of fabric.

[Antichloro treatment
↓
Decomp. of cotton]

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2. Uneven bleaching: Uneven bleaching due to

- (a) Less strength of bleaching agent
- (b) Insufficient dosing and dosing of bleaching chemical is not timely.
- (c) Mechanical fault in m/c
- (d) Circulation of bleaching liquor and fabric is not properly.
- (e) Also for uneven scouring, uneven bleaching occurs.

3. Improper bleaching: Uneven bleaching itself an improper bleaching. Improper bleaching refers to the bleaching which is not exactly suitable for over predetermined shade. For light shade high reflectance of bleaching and for dark shade not well but moderate reflectance of bleaching is done.

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For example, half bleach (less H_2O_2 , less time it is done quickly) in dark shade but in pale/light shade full bleach is done.

5. Alkalinity may remain: If alkalinity may remain in fabric generally CH_3COOH is used to remove alkalinity.

6. Test of alkalinity: For test of alkalinity, fabric immersed in some water and shocking for (2-3) hours. Now by pH paper alkalinity is test. If red paper becomes blue, then we sure that fabric may have alkalinity.

Remedy: Fabric must be neutralized.

6. Residual Peroxide: After bleaching (8-10)% of residual peroxide is remain in bath. It cannot be remove by washing. It remove at least (1-2)% still remain in fabric. In this condition, it will use dye, peroxide reacts with dye.

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6) Iron bacteria is inherently in water, it create problem when related to pH. Iron bacteria is active in acidic pH. Iron bacteria excrete in the form of hydrated oxide $[Fe(OH)_3]$ it is slowed in pipe line and gather in pipe line - when the layer of $Fe(OH)_3$ is about 1mm, it may separate from the pipe line and entered into the processing zone and caused the fabric iron marks which is difficult to remove.

Remedy:

① If chlorination is done in water, iron bacteria is killed.

② Oxalic acid treatment is done to remove this fault.

③ The processed fabric is got stiffed after oxalic acid treatment after dyeing the fabric is softer by using following agent:

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*** What do you understand by colour fastness

Ans: Colour fastness is the resistance

property of some dyed textile material
(treated with some of the chemical or physical

agencies)

Ex:

1. Colour fastness to wash
2. Colour fastness to perspiration
3. Colour fastness to rubbing
4. Colour fastness to light
5. Colour fastness to chlorine water
6. Colour fastness to sea water
7. Colour fastness to water
8. Colour fastness to saliva (নান)

Colour fastness to wash:

Specimen dimension:

4cm x 10cm

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ISO method: IV

Developed Soap - 5 gm/L
Anhydrous Sodium carbonate - 2 gm/L
Temp - 95°C
Time - 30 min
M:L = 1:50

ISO method: V

Soap - 5 gm/L
Anhydrous Sodium carbonate 2 gm/L
Temp - 95°C
Time - 4 hours
M:L = 1:50

Composite specimen

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intended to determine the tenistance of colour of dyed textile to the action of acid and alkali peracipitation.

Test procedure :

Two artificial peracipitation solutions are made up as follows.

Solution	
(A)	(B)
0.5 gm	0.5 gm
5 gm	5 gm
2.5 gm	2.5 gm

chemicals:

L- Histidine - mono hydrochloride Solution

	A	B
Mono hydrtzle	0.5 gm	0.5 gm
Sodium chloride	5 gm	5 gm
Di- sodium hydrogen ortho-phosphate ($Na_2HPO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$)	2.5 gm	2.5 gm

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Solution

	(A)	(B)
Volume of distilled H ₂ O	1000 ml	1000 ml
pH (adjusted with N/10 NaOH)	8	5.8

* Name of dye: **Petrol picrozoetetz.**

Procedure:

The material to be tested is placed between two undyed pieces, one of which is of the same piece fabric and the other is as follows -

If first piece is		The second will be
cotton	_____	wool
wool	_____	cotton
Silk	_____	wool
Linen	_____	wool

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Vincelone — wool
Cellulose acetate — vincelone
Polyamide — wool/vincelone
Polyester — wool/vincelone
Acrylic — wool/vincelone

The pieces are sewn along one side to form a composite specimen. This is thoroughly wetted out in 50 times its weight of the artificial perspiration solution (A). It is allowed to remain in the solution for 30 minutes at room temperature, after which the liquid is poured off.

The specimen is then placed between two glass plates (acrylic glass plate 11.5 cm x 6.0 cm x 1.5 cm) pressed together with a force equivalent to 4.5 kg (10 lb) and allowed to stand in an oven at 37°C ± 2°C for 4 hours.

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After this, the dyed and undyed samples are separated and they are all dried at a temperature not exceeding 60°C.

The procedure is repeated with solution (B). The changes of colour and staining are then assessed with grey scale for each test.

Test specimen preparation:

If the textile to be tested is fabric, then sample size is (4cm x 10cm)

*** Discuss about colour fastness to rubbing?

Ans:

Sample: (15 x 15) cm

This tests determine the fastness of a dyestuff to either cut or dry rubbing.

Equipment:

1. Crock meter
2. Grey scale for staining
3. stop watch

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Test specimen: Two pieces of fabric (15 cm x 5 cm)
are required for dry rubbing and two
for wet rubbing.

Test procedure:

Dry rubbing test:

Lock the test specimen onto the base of the
crookmeter so that it lies flat and taut
for testing.

Using the optical spring dip net a (5 cm x 5 cm)
square of white cotton rubbing test cloth
(desized, bleached but without finished) to
the fingers (peg) of the crookmeter. Lower
the fingers onto the test sample, fingers
create 9 Newton pressure on fabric.

Turn the handcrank and make ten complete
turns of this crank at the rate of one
turn per second i.e. 10 turns in 10 seconds.

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Remove the white rubbing cloth from the finger and evaluate color transfer using gray scale for staining under standard light. One test is done to water/water direction another for wet/water direction.

Wet rubbing test:

Here only white cotton cloth is wetted in distilled water and set it to finger (peg) of the crock meter without squeezing.

Evaluation:

Compare the colour contrast between the treated and untreated white rubbing cloth with staining gray scale.

For dry rubbing test one rating for water/water direction, another for

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Wet/course direction.

For wet tubbing test one rating for warp/wales direction, another for wet/course direction.

So final result will be the average of grading of warp and wet or wales and course direction.

Write down the definition of colour.

Ans:

In 1922, the committee on colorimetry of the optical society of America give a nice definition of colour.

Colour is a general name for all sensation arising from the activity of the retina of the eye and its attached to the nervous mechanism, this activity being in nearly every case in the normal individual, a specific response to radiant energy of certain wavelength and intensity.

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*** Write down the definition of "Light"

Ans: Light is an electromagnetic radiation that consists of radiant energy of which a human observer is aware through visual sensation arising from the stimulation of the retina of the eye.

*** Write down the chronological development of colour?

Ans. Since Isaac Newton separated white day-light into a sequence of colored light called spectrum (1704)

↓
Trichromatic theory (Proposed by)

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On 1852 Helmholtz first recognize the difference between additive and subtractive theory of color mixing.

Additive theory: Additive theory is called light theory. Now light theory is described below -

Fig: Schematic diagram of additive color mixing.

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1. In light theory the primary colors are red, green and blue. The mixing of these 3-primary colors in equal quantity produce white light.

2. The addition of the three primaries with one another gives the following colors.

- 1 part red + 1 part Green = Yellow
- 1 part Green + 1 part Blue = Cyan
- 1 part Blue + 1 part red = Magenta

The resultant three colors i.e. Yellow, cyan and magenta are called secondary color.

This theory is used in color television.

*** Discuss briefly subtractive theory/
Pigment theory

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1. In Pigment theory the primary colours are Red, Yellow, Blue. The mixing of these three colours in equal quantity will produce black shade.

2. In addition of these three primary give the following colours.

1 part red + 1 part yellow = Orange

1 part yellow + 1 part blue = Green

1 part blue + 1 part red = Violet

These three colours i.e orange, green and violet are secondary colours.

This theory is used in textile color mixing.

Mid Term Write down the Elements/ Properties/ Attributes of color ?

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Each color has its own distinct appearance based on three elements - Hue, chroma, value

By describing a color using these three attributes, we can accurately identify a particular color and distinguish it from any other.

Hue: Hue is the first attributes of color-order system, by which we identify a sample simply hue is how we perceive an object color such as red, orange, green, blue etc. hue is the around color of color wheel.

Value: The second characteristics of color describes its luminous intensity that it is its degree of lightness value is the amount of black mixed with the hue. Color can be classified as light or dark when comparing their value.

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Fig: Schematic diagram of three dimensional color system.

It is established in 1931.
The full meaning of CIE is commission internationale de l'Eclairage,
translated as the international commission on Illumination, this body

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Vertical axis: Technical part of
responsible for international harmonization
photometry and colorimetry.
The aim of CIE is to tell us, how a color
might be produced (By mixing of
three primaries). The amount of three
primaries required to match a
particulate color provide a numerical
specification of that color. A different
color would require different amounts
of the primaries and have the
specification would be different.
*** Discuss briefly, color Measurement
Numerical expression of color?
Ans: In 1976 CIE expressed color
numerically with the help of CIE Lab
Uniform color space (Three medium
expression)

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Now expressing color numerically by
CIE Lab color space is describe below:

In CIE Lab system -

1. L^* axis is vertical. The centre L^* axis shown $L=100$ at the top is white or total reflection and $L=0$ at the bottom represent black or total absorption. At the centre of this plane is neutral or grey (Achromatic point)
2. a^* axis is horizontal and perpendicular to L^* . where $+a^*$ value indicates red hue and $-a^*$ value indicates green value.
3. b^* axis is horizontal and perpendicular to both L^* and a^* axis $+b^*$ value indicates yellow hue and $-b^*$ value indicates blue hue.

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Discuss briefly color difference?

Ans: In CIE $L^* a^* b^*$ color space, the color difference between standard and trial sample is expressed mathematically by ΔE and color difference in coordination can be resolved into three components to give an indication of the magnitude and direction of color difference between standard and trial sample.

Resolve = বিচ্ছেদ করা
 ignore = গুরুত্ব না দেওয়া
 Trial = Examination
 Coordinate = স্থানাঙ্ক

$$\Delta E_{ab}^* = (\Delta L^{*2} + \Delta a^{*2} + \Delta b^{*2})^{1/2}$$

Here ① $\Delta L^* = L_T^* - L_S^*$

② $\Delta a^* = a_T^* - a_S^*$

③ $\Delta b^* = b_T^* - b_S^*$

- ① ΔL^* (+) Lighter, (-) darker
 ② Δa^* (+) Redder, (-) Greener
 ③ Δb^* (+) Yellower, (-) Bluer

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Practically zero color difference

($\Delta E = 0$) is impossible. Even in a same

place of a colored sample if see test

twice, the instrument will show some

color difference, so, there is an acceptable

range of color difference -

if $\Delta E \leq 1$, acceptable color match

Perfectly

if $\Delta E > 1$, unacceptable, color doesn't match.

But it depends on also in visual assessment if color match visually (i.e. visually looks good) the value of ΔE is ignored.

Solvent Scattering

vapor lock "

Tortman

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Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh; 17 May 2023.

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d) Solvent scouring: For the presence of alkali and caustic and high temperature solvent scouring is occurred to remove wax, oil and adhesive. Time - 15-30 second.

Q. What do you understand by optical brightening agent (OBA)

Ans: Optical brightening agents are colorless or very pale yellow colored organic compounds which added to a substrate increase the reflectance in the visible region by converting ultra-violet radiation into visible light and thus increase the whiteness or brightness. Optical brightening agents can also be called

1. Fluorescent brightening agent.
2. Fluorescent whiteners.
3. Physical bleaching agents
4. Brightener.

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The result obtain in the distribution of reflected light becomes more uniform through out the spectral range and the surface becomes apparently white, so it is called physical bleaching agent.

Fig: showing whitening effects of different treatment.

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~~Q. Write down the types of OBA?~~

Ans:

Optical brightening agents are of three types.

1. OBA with reddish hue

2. OBA with bluish hue

3. OBA with greenish hue.

1. Reddish hue: It is a derivatives of di-amino stilbene disulphonic acid.

Ex: Blancophote R (UK, Livetec brothers)

Fig: Blancophote R

2. OBA with Bluish hue: This is the mostly used and preferred OBA.

Ex: Blancophote B (UK, Livetec brothers)

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*** Write down trade name of OBA

Ans: C1=CC=C(C=C1)N(C)C(=O)N2C=CC=CC=C2

Trade Name	Manufacturer	Origin
Uvitex	Ciba	Switzerland
Leucophot	Clariant	Switzerland
ultraphot	BASF	Germany
Tainapol	ciba (Hentol)	Switzerland
Mega white	Matex (Apex)	Bangladesh
Synowhite	Everohine	Bang.
Flou-white	Dygnin-chem	Bang.

(BB) (BB) (BB)

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Write down the application process of OBA:

Ans: Optical brighteners are mostly applied on cotton textile materials.

Treatment of OBA is rarely carried out in a separate process. It is usually incorporated with some finishing process and sometime in a same bath of scouring and bleaching. Optical brighteners can be applied by -

- (1) Exhaust method
- (2) Padding method

Recipe:

Wetting agent - 0.5 g/L
Leveling agent - 0.5 g/L

Sequestering agent - 1-2 g/L

Caustic soda - 2 g/L

H₂O₂

Soda ash - 3 g/L

Stabilizer - 2-3 g/L

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Write down the application process of OBA

URI-tex-2B — 0.5% sof

Temp — 98°C

Time — 30 min

Applied on cotton textile

Treatment of OBA in the process of dyeing

Auxiliaries: 200g/l OBA

90°C

shade check

15 min 30 min

bottom printing

Fig: OBA treatment process.

(OBA - top printing is not possible)
 (OBA - bottom printing is possible)

Aster treatment:

Hot wash (80°C)

↓

Hot wash (70-80°C), 10 min

↓

Hot wash (70°C)

Cold wash

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Q. Describe briefly about spectrophotometer

Ans: A colour measurement spectrophotometer follows the simple theory of color vision. A light source is used to illuminate the sample using a specific illumination and viewing geometry. Reflected or transmitted light is then pass into spectral analyzer where light is split into its spectral components. The light detector and control electronics to make measurements across the visible spectrum.

Spectrophotometers have three essential parts:-

- (1) a light source
- (2) a monochromator
- (3) a detector

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(1) A light source such as tungsten lamp by equally provides the illuminant for spectrophotometer.

(2) A monochromator is a prism or diffraction grating which splits the light from the source into a spectrum. The monochromator and slit selects a narrow band of light to be measured.

Fig: Basic principle of a spectrophotometer

SAW
LAV
Detector array
Electronics
Computer
Spectral Analyzing
Dispersing grating

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The main parts of dual beam spectrophotometer are mentioned below -

1. Light Source: The lamp in the spectrophotometer is a pulsed Xenon lamp. The lamp is filtered to make it illuminate like D65. The UV filter can be or cannot be used.

2. Specular port: It is a glom-trap. Diffuse light beam falls on specular port. The reflected light from specular port falls on sample and then is collected by lens. This light is bright and shiny. This is called specular reflection.

3. Spectral Analyzer: Spectral Analyzer is the key part of this device. It splits light to its spectral components.

১. আলোক উৎস
২. স্পেকুলার পোর্ট
৩. স্পেকট্রাল অ্যানালাইজার

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Diffracting grating: Grating is a film or surface containing close equidistance and parallel line used for producing spectra by diffraction.

Mirrors: Mirrors are produced by evaporating metals onto glass or quartz under vacuum, by aluminium, copper, silver and gold. The spectral reflectance of mirrors is always higher than any polished surface of metal.

Integrating sphere is a hollow sphere coated inside with white $BaSO_4$ (reflectance 98.5%). The sphere is 152 mm in diameter.

Integrating sphere is used for color measurement of the surface of the material.

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Butternut printing
It is a drastic process and it involves at least part of the fabric in the printed area will be destroyed. In butternut printing the removal of one part of substrate is essential, to desired effect.

The principle of this printing is that the print paste contain an agent that is capable of dissolving (carbonizing) or destroying the fabric in the printed area during subsequent printing process.

~~***~~ cotton/polyester blend is an ideal for butternut printing where polyester portion of the fabric is unaffected

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by reagent used to destroy the cellulose portion. Here by carbonizing cotton part is dissolved and polyester part remains in fabric. The reagent generate a strong acid (40% H₂SO₄) during subsequent heat treatment after printing and make hydrolytic dissolve in cotton part and allow a mentionable burnout effect with adequate strength and stability. This style is apply on cotton to give novel denim fabric effect.

Wool/Polyester: H.W. (NaOH) Printing book miles. P(207)

Fabric resembling leather appearance after B.P. printing and leather articles are also produced different effect can be imported by -

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1. Solid colored or white effect: Here the blend is dyed or printed by disperse dye only. Such dyeing or printing

will show chalky or delustrated appearance due to undyed cellulose portion. In those areas where cellulose is removed by burn out produced full depth of color of dyed polyester.

2. Contrast color effect:

The style can be extended further by burn out printing a burn out paste on fabric which is previously subjected to discharge process in which two fibres have been dyed by contrasting color. Such an style offers a wide variety of possible effect.

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Recipe of Bore printing

Diopetase dye - x gm

Water - 120 gm

Sodium hydrogen sulphate - 240 gm

Salt low cost bean gum - 400 gm
cust

Glycerin - 80 gm

Carriers - 0-15 gm

Urea - 0-10 gm

Propetly dry - 100°C

Heat treatment - 180°-220°C

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~~***~~ Discuss briefly about transfer printing
Recipe of Dye transfer printing

Ans: Transfer printing in textile means the sublimation of dyes from a colored design on paper at high temp followed by absorption of dye vapours by synthetic fibres in the fabric.

Sublimation: Vapour of individual molecule

So, the process of transfer printing consists of transferring the colored design from pre-printed paper to fabric under the action of controlled condition of temperature, time and pressure.

France → 1958 . first used
1968 . commercially in market.

~~***~~ Write down the condition for transfer printing?

Ans: ... in the ... of

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1. Types of dyes: That types of dyes which are sublime at high temp. have sublimation property for synthetic fabric to be printed, but have no affinity for the pre-printed paper.

2. The molecular weight of these dyes falls in the range from 230-370

3. The dye should readily sublime at around 200°C temp.

4. The synthetic fibre fabric should have necessary physical, chemical and thermoplastic properties to withstand sufficient processing temp.

5. The printing paper must meet the high quality for design

6. A method of transferring the design from paper to fabric is needed.

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Q. How to select dyestuff for T. Printing.

Ans: The dyes must have sublime at high temp. and must also have adequate fastness to washing and hot pressing.

When printing with dye mixture, compatible dyes with comparable transfer properties are essential to ensure color constancy.

Two important properties for dye selection are -

1. The molecular weight of the dyes ranges from (200-370)

2. The dyes should be transferred at (200-210)°C within 20 sec.

Q. Write down the list of some suitable dyes for transfer printing.

Process

Ans:

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Brand Name	Manufacturer
C.I. Dispersed yellow 3	Mono azo
C.I. Dispersed yellow 12	Nitro diphenyl amine
C.I. Dispersed red 4	Anthraquinone
C.I. Dispersed red 13	Mono azo
C.I. Dispersed violet	Anthraquinone
Brand Name	Manufacturer
Tetra print	Ciba geigy/Huntsman
Transforon	Sandoz/clarient
Resoline dyes	F-Bayetz
Latyl dyes	Du-pont

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~~Write down~~ Write down the quality of printing paper?

Ans:

1. Paper weighting from (35-115) GSM have been used depending on printing method.
2. The paper should be sufficiently strong to prevent the tearing in high speed printing.
3. The paper should exhibit good 'hold out' that the liquid ink should not penetrate the paper surface and have stability to hold the image.
4. The paper has dimensionally stable during printing.
5. Good release of the dye vapour from the ink layer.

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6. Stability to heat upto 220°C

7. Paper should have a smooth surface and should free from metal. because some disperse dyes are metal sensitive.

*** Write down the ingredient of printing ink ?

Ans: Ink used in transfer printing are made up of -

1. Dye stuff
2. Vehicles (solvent)
3. Thickeners.

Now these are described below:

(i) Some selected and special quality dye stuff with the required req characteristics are used as dye stuff for making ink. They these dyes should sublime at high temp.

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(2) Vehicles makes the dyestuff dissolved
eg. solvent, spirit, glycol, Toluene,
ethyl-methyl keton

(3) Thickeners act as a binding agent
and impart necessary viscosity. eg-
Polyvinyl acetate, cellulose, ester,
acrylic resin etc.

~~Q~~ Write down the types of transfer printing?

Ans:

1. Sublimation/ Dry heat/ vapour phase transfer printing.

2. Melt transfer printing.

3. Film release transfer printing.

4. Wet or migration transfer printing.

Book tests.

Def 1

Def 2

Def 3

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*** Discuss briefly, mechanism of transfer printing.

$t=0$
 starting
 position

In process

Before
 finish
 heat
 press

Here, $F = \text{Fabric}$

$P = \text{Printed paper}$

$I = \text{Printing ink}$

$G_2 = \text{Gap}$

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2. Melt transfer printing:

In melt transfer the design is printed on paper using a waxy ink. When a hot iron is pressed to its reverse side against the fabric the ink melts in contact with it. It is also called state printing or thermochromic printing.

4. Wet or migration transfer printing:

In this process water soluble dyes are incorporated into printing ink which is used to produce design on paper. This design is transferred to a moistened textile using carefully regulated contact pressure. The dye is transferred by diffusion through the aqueous medium. This method is not used at present.

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